

**BA(Hons)
[Business management]**

**RESEARCH ON THE PERFORMANCE OF AGRICULTURAL START-UP BUSINESSES
(ASBs) IN UGANDA]**

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DECLARATION;

This dissertation is submitted in partial fulfillment of the BA (Hons) [Business management]

I declare that this dissertation is my own original work and has not been submitted elsewhere in fulfillment of the requirements of this or any other award.

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i) ABBREVIATIONS;

ASBs	Agricultural Startup Businesses
PBB	Priority Based Budgeting
TB	Traditional Budgeting
GDP	Gross Domestic Product

SMEs	Small Medium Enterprises
RCB	Risk Centric Budgeting
BBA	Beyond Budgeting Approach
NSBSU	National Small business Survey of Uganda
ILO	International Labor Organisation

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v) ABSTRACT;

The study aims to discover how agricultural start-up businesses (ASBs) in Uganda might make the most use of budgeting to improve their financial performance. Questionnaires and interviews were used to obtain primary data from ASBs founders, managers, treasurers, and secretaries. This study's sample size of (27) people was chosen using a convenient sampling approach. This was also a major limitation of this research as the recommendations are universal yet based on such a limited sample. This research highlights a notable variance within Ugandan ASBs.

Despite the fact that these start-ups make up the majority of small firms, they have not had a detectable positive influence because they financially fail in the early stages of their life cycles. According to Ugandan Economic Review research, a significant number of these young business owners lack the requisite skills to create comprehensive budgets. Moreover, they also employ traditional tools and budgeting methods that are rigid and cannot catch up with the dynamic business environment. This has resulted in inefficient resource allocation, overspending, and cash flow concerns. However, In contrast to the inefficient budgeting

element, findings demonstrate that financial failures encompass other issues such as political instabilities and insufficient financial support from institutions. This study is significant to the society as it addresses start-ups financial failure that is affecting the Ugandan agricultural sector hence the country's economy. Recommendations derived from this study emphasize the vital importance of implementing effective budgeting strategies within these start-ups. These include investment in budget literacy, modern tools, adoption of the stakeholder theory, diversifying funding sources and adaptability. These measures are imperative for enhancing the financial resilience of start-ups and, consequently, contributing to the overall economic stability of Uganda.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background context

The agricultural industry in Uganda continues to be unparalleled, expected to employ roughly 70% of the population and produce approximately 26% of GDP (Jaramillo, 2018; Douglas et al., 2017; Dalberg, 2011). Agriculture has been legally recognized by the government as an important economic sector in Uganda's progress toward middle-income status. As a clear indication of its commitment, the government has increased its financial contribution to the farm sector budget by an incredible 65% (Andrew, 2022). Food and cash crops provide for around 20% of total export earnings and one-third of foreign exchange receipts, according to (IAG) Infant Agriculture Uganda (2022).

Figure B1: Real per capita GDP (PPP) growth rate, in percent (smoothened)

Source: World Development Indicators, World Bank staff calculations

Figure 1 ; Economic growth rebounds in Uganda. (Source; Jaramallo, 2018)

Figure 1 demonstrates how Uganda's GDP has rebound since 1996 with agriculture being one of the main contributors (Jaramillo, 2018).

Enhancing the financial resilience of start-ups is therefore vital as agriculture is expected to make a significant contribution to the overall economic stability of Uganda.

Given the scarcity of resources and the intense rivalry that plague agricultural businesses, the budgetary truth becomes even more obvious (Skala, 2018). Budgets can be powerful tools for planning and control when used properly, especially in the case of start-up businesses' improved performance (Scott and Enu-Kwesi, 2018).

Performance refers to how successfully and efficiently a company achieves its goals and objectives (Chodankar et al, 2020). On the other hand, financial performance is a comprehensive assessment of a company's financial health over a given time period (Simpson, Simkins and Cater, 2010). According to San and Heng (2011), this assessment takes into account a variety of metrics, including a company's cash flow, working capital, cost structure, borrowing activities, and overall growth trajectory.

This research is crafted with the intention of mitigating technical deficiencies in the accounting systems of start-up businesses. Subbotina (2014) suggests that through budgeting, business startups can effectively allocate their resources, streamline task coordination, and manage costs and cash flows. Budgetary control entails creating a financial blueprint and comparing actual spending to it on a regular basis to see if adjustments are required to stay on the desired route (Scott Enu-Kwesi, 2018) .

This process is essential for controlling expenses and achieving a variety of financial goals (Scott and Enu-Kwesi, 2018). In both the public and commercial sectors, organizations rely largely on budgetary control to oversee their financial endeavors (Dunk, 2009). While tracking these different financial aspects, start-ups can ultimately improve their financial performance through evaluating, adjusting and regulating their incomes (Stange, Bogsnes & Sheth, 2021).

Moreover this approach enables assessing and investing of financial managerial roles and their effectiveness (Mbogo et al, 2021). This includes whether the manager is executing appropriate actions and effectiveness or whether they are accomplishing their tasks with optimal resource utilization (Scott Enu-Kwesi, 2018). Simultaneously, it's plausible that results or information from the budget exert significant influence on the managers' responses and reaction, hence their subsequent action towards the betterment of the businesses (Mbogo et al, 2021)

1.2 Rationale of the study

Agricultural startup businesses (ASBs) in Uganda exhibit elevated business financial failure rates (Neszmélyi and Késmárki-Gally, 2019).

According to Ezra et al. (2014), around 70% of ASBs in Uganda stop operations within the first three years. This trend is not specific to Uganda; it is observed in a number of nations throughout the world. According to Arora (2023), about half of all firm debuts in the United Kingdom fail within three years. Even in other southern African countries, the failure rate is expected to be (70%-80%), with a frightening 70% occurring in the initial year, as stated (Rabie, Cant, & Wiid, 2016).

Considering these worrisome rates of business failure, governments around the world continue to place a heavy emphasis on the critical importance of young enterprises (European Union, 2023). They hold high expectations for the valuable contributions of these businesses to GDP, job opportunities, wealth accumulation, economic growth, and the engagement of a significant number of unemployed youths, especially in developing countries (Kuschel et al, 2018; Decker et al, 2014).

Consequently, governments, development partners, and industry experts have faced a significant challenge posed by the high failure rates of Agricultural Start-Up Businesses (ASBs). They have introduced and experimented with various interventions and support programs, encompassing training(Choi et al, 2021), tax incentives (Tibeingana, 2022; Verbena, 2017), and financial literacy (Christone, 2019; Anitah, 2022). They have also introduced cost accounting methodologies (Bangomin et al., 2015), strategic management accounting approaches (

Akenbor & Akoye, 2012), as well as other strategic measures. Unfortunately, the persistently high rates of ASBs financial failures continue to be a pressing issue.

According to CEA (2013), even though these startups constitute a significant portion of small businesses, they have failed to make a discernible positive impact as they frequently falter during the early stages of their development (Nou and Dehane, 2023).

According to the (Pimpong Relyea, 2016), agricultural start-ups in Uganda have often encountered financial dilemmas that stem from inadequate financial planning and budgeting practices. Given the agricultural sector's large prospects for job creation, wealth production, and GDP contributions, its financial success has a huge impact on a country's overall economic well-being. As a result, the purpose of this research is to investigate how budgeting strategies can be made effective enough to boost the financial success of agricultural startup firms in Uganda.

According to research conducted by the Ugandan Economic Review (2023), a substantial number of these young business owners lack the necessary abilities to establish complete budgets, resulting in inefficient resource allocation, overspending, and cash flow issues. This is especially true when unanticipated expenses arise, such as equipment repairs, pest outbreaks, or unforeseen market shifts.

1.3 Research Question

What are the potential strategies or interventions that could be introduced to help agricultural start-ups implement effective budgeting systems in order to facilitate their access to long-term capital for innovation and growth?

1.4.1 Aim

The aim of this research is to foster individual and organizational learning concerning the role of budgeting and how agricultural start-ups in Uganda can implement budgeting practices efficiently in order to improve their financial performance.

1.4.2 Research Objectives

- To assess the existing budgeting practices employed by agricultural start-ups in Uganda, identifying their strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.
- To analyze the specific financial challenges and dilemmas faced by agricultural start-ups in Uganda that can be mitigated through the effective implementation of budgeting practices.
- To explore the barriers and obstacles that agricultural start-ups encounter when attempting to adopt and implement budgeting practices within their operational strategies.
- To develop practical guidelines and recommendations tailored to the unique context of agricultural start-ups in Uganda, aimed at facilitating the successful integration of budgeting practices to enhance financial performance.

1.5 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research follows a pragmatic philosophy. Pragmatism emphasizes the practical implications of research findings (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). In addition, an inductive approach is employed to build theory from research findings, following the methodology outlined by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019)

A mixed-method approach to data collection is employed to achieve complete results. This method provides for a more in-depth investigation of the research issue, utilizing both quantitative and qualitative data sources (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). As a result, the study combined data from questionnaires and interviews. This strategy improves the strength and validity of research findings (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

1.6 Dissertation Structure

This research report is divided into 5 sections. The Introduction establishes the framework for the study and introduces the topic: "Investigating into the role of budgeting on the financial

performance of agricultural start-up businesses (ASBs) in Uganda" This chapter also defines the research's justification and goals.

The literature review segment engages analysis of existing literature. It will explore various budgeting approaches, intricacies of financial performance, challenges within budgeting processes, and diverse budgeting methods. This fundamental chapter lays the foundation for the study's context and significance. The methodology chapter will clarify the techniques utilized in this research. Its purpose is to provide readers with a clear understanding of the reasoning behind each method.

The findings and discussions chapter will offer a comprehensive exploration of research results. The concluding chapter will recap the research, restating its aims and objectives, and addressing any limitations and challenges encountered during the study. It will serve as a platform for reflecting on the study's accomplishments and will provide recommendations for future researchers undertaking similar projects. The structure will be completed with a reference list and any relevant appendices, enhancing the overall content.

Moving into the next chapter, the literature review directs our focus to the broader landscape of enhancing financial performance through effective budgeting.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW;

2.1 Introduction;

The Literature review chapter, according to Torraco (2015), is a critical study of current academic literature. The goal of this chapter is to look at what other authors have learned about the impact of budgeting methods on the financial performance of agricultural start-up businesses (ASBs) in Uganda. Goldstein et al., (2018) and Lutz et al., (2018) underline the need of doing a literature review to identify existing gaps in any particular field. As a result, this chapter covers financial gaps in (ASBs) budgeting systems, agricultural start-ups, and areas where additional research is needed. The following is how this chapter is organized: an examination of the (ASBS) and related ideas, budgeting theories and methods, the impact of budgeting on financial performance, and criticism of the existing literature.

2.2 Unique context of ASBs in Uganda.

Startups in Uganda are categorized based on the number of employees, firm size, Age of existence, market size, number of resources (Nurcahyo, Akbae & Gabriel, 2018); (Lee, 2016). Startups fall under several categories including Micro-start-ups that employ less than 49 employees making 71% of (SMES) (Andersen, 2012); (Greenbank, 2020). Startups exist at different levels including Small-Scale, medium-scale (50-59 employees) and Large-scale agri-startups that employ over (100) workers (Kumbhat and Sshil, 2018).

Figure 2; Distribution of start-ups by size (Source;(NSBSU) National Small business Survey of Uganda, 2015)

In the agricultural sector of Uganda, the most predominant feature of these start-ups is that they are owned by people who want to be agents of change in their families and communities (Stenholm and Hytti, 2014). They mainly intend to make a profit besides their social concerns (Bairwa et al., 2014). Since these entrepreneurs control over 30%-100% of their business, they are mainly concerned with cost minimisation in order to earn a profit (Berglann et al., 2011). Hence, relying on cost effective labor, technology and other investments. This is because capital is always limited as analyzed by the (NSBSU) National small businesses Survey of Uganda (2015). Besides start-ups that are lucky to have investors, 80% of the clear majority use their own funds to implement their businesses. Other sources include support of 6.7% from

friends and families, 3.8% bank loans, microfinance loans 0.4 % and others from donations of approximately 2.8% (NSBSU, 2015).

	Total %	Micro %	Small %	Medium %
Own funds	86.3	88	83	82
Friends/family funds	6.7	6	8	9
Bank loan	3.8	3	6	4
Microfinance loan	0.4	0	0	1
Other (church fund, donations, government)	2.8	2	4	5

FIG 3; (Source; National Small business Survey of Uganda, 2015)

In this instance, where capital investment is restricted, it is critical for these start-up owners to use strategies that help them manage, account for, and prepare for their funds (Annessi-Pessina et al., 2020). This is because, despite their enormous importance, such as contributing 66% to employment, they continue to collapse due to bankruptcy concerns (Sullivan, 2017). According to a report, demand for agricultural products has increased over the last decade (Ayo, Bonabana-Wabbi, & Sserunkuuma, 2020); (Ekou, 2014). Thus, these start-ups have been capable of making 72% of their income from selling produce to their community members, 50.7% from value-added farm produce products, and almost 25% from direct-to-consumer sales (Sullivan, 2017); (Land & Matrix, 2015). Therefore, it is worth highlighting that the cause of this financial failure is not a drop in sales, but rather a failure to manage finances (Pimpong Relyea, 2016). According to the (BHRRC) Business and Human Rights resource center (2023), inadequate financial planning does breed misallocation of resources which in turn leads to unaccountable cash outflow that leads to bankruptcy.

2.3 THEORIES OF BUDGETARY;

One common budgeting theory is the traditional budgeting system (TBS), in which organizations build budgets based on previous financial data (Nemec and Vries, 2019). It suggests that the prior year's budget be used as the foundation for the current budget (Liyanagea, Gooneratnea, 20210). It has been lauded for saving time and measuring performance over time, especially in stable environments (Atim and Elia, 2017; Halilic & Kassem, 2021). It simplifies resource allocation for entrepreneurial teams that must focus on developing their agricultural methods

rather than wasting time on detailed budget preparation (Adullahi, 2011). However, Traditional budgets (TB), according to Rakia and Minela (2022); Liyanage & Gooneratnea (2021) fail to adapt to changes in a dynamic business environment, rendering them outmoded and ineffective. Traditional budgeting (TB) is characterized as an outmoded technique by Atim and Elias (2017), while Wolf (2020) and Sauter and Horvath (2020) label it as 'ineffective' and 'unnecessary evil,' respectively.

In response to complaints of traditional budgeting, modern businesses have shifted to better budgeting and the beyond budgeting approach (BBA) or modern budgeting (Liyanagea, Gooneratnea, 2021); (Marcus, 2015). BBA is defined as a budgetary method that uses current or up-to-date financial data (Kumareswaran, 2019; Al-ddin, 2021). It is a rolling strategy in which budgets are modified on a monthly or quarterly basis (Al-ddin, 2021). Despite its benefits, Al-ddin (2021) claims that it is more time-consuming and difficult to install than standard methods. However, the advantages of flexibility, and improved performance monitoring frequently exceed the disadvantages, making contemporary budgeting a preferred choice for many Agricultural Startup businesses. ASBs operate in a dynamic environment in terms of weather, politics, price fluctuations and cultural dynamics thus BBA approach suits better than Traditional methods (Nauges and Chavas, 2020); (Borodin. Bourtembourg & Labadie, 2016)

2.4 BUDGETING METHODS

2.4.1 PRIORITY BASED BUDGETING (PBB)

PBB is considered as a modern budgeting approach that assesses the relative relevance of particular programs and services as opposed to entire departments (Lynch et al.,2017). It distinguishes itself by ranking the programs provided in order of importance (Mitchel et al., 2021). PBB is crucial in resource allocation since it aligning resources with corporate goals, hence providing appealing strategy for agricultural entrepreneurs (Lynch et al.,2017). It has the potential to improve the efficiency and efficacy of resource management inside these companies by encouraging a focus on efforts that directly contribute to their goals, such as increasing crop yields or implementing sustainable practices (Hall et. al, 2017); (Kavanagh et al., 2011).

However, it is critical to recognize potential difficulties in applying Priority-Based Budgeting within agricultural companies. One significant difficulty is the subjectivity of priority. Various

factors, including individual biases and preferences, can influence what constitutes a high-priority effort (Kavanagh et al., 2010). Furthermore, in the case of agricultural startups, external variables such as weather and market fluctuations can have a substantial impact on priorities, making it critical for businesses to be responsive in their budgeting procedures (Nauges and Chavas, 2020); (Borodin. Bourtembourg & Labadie, 2016). Therefore, Mitchell (2014) emphasizes that continual monitoring and evaluation of budgeted projects is critical to ensure that resources are allocated properly.

2.4.2 INCREMENTAL BUDGETING;

Incremental budgeting is dominated by the aspects of the (TB) traditional budgeting approach that crafting budgets and adjusting them in dependency of the previous years' financial allocations (Schick, 2014); (Beredugo, Azubike & Okon, 2019). This method was founded by Aaron Wildavsky while in his research of the 1960's. According to the (EJBM) European Journal of Business and Management (2016), this method is crucial in times of crisis such as war. Here, organizations may depend on the provisional records of actual expenditures from the prior fiscal year in cases when expected statistics for the current fiscal year are not readily available (Beredugo, Azubike & Okon, 2019); (Greenwood et al., 2022). This strategy has the benefit of consistency and predictability, which can be especially helpful in the agricultural sector that is susceptible to outside risks like the weather and market swing (EJBM, 2013).

Critics of this theory point to a fundamental failure to focus on efficiency and a proclivity to carry over difficulties to the next because the same criteria are continuously applied each year (Oussini, 2018); Silva, 2015). The Incremental Budgeting approach, which focuses on incremental innovations to existing solutions, hinders the introduction of new ideas (Arregle et al., 2015). Scholars such as Marcus (2015), Liyanagea and Gooneratnea (2021), and Atim and Elias (2017) have repeated this difficulty, with low quality innovation extending beyond Uganda

to the entire African continent in comparison to other continents (Moreira & Mehra, 2022).

Figure 4; Innovation in Africa (Source; Moreira & Mehra, 2022).

Figure 4 indicates how Incremental budgeting perpetuates a cycle of incremental innovation in Africa, resulting in a prevalence of low-quality innovations. This detrimental trend contributes to the continent's inferior ranking among regions, significantly impeding overall development.

2.4.3 THE RISK CENTRIC BUDGETING METHOD (RCB)

RCB emphasizes the significance of integrating risk factors into the budgeting process to enhance investment decision-making and minimize the uncertainties tied to investments (Pipelines, 2018); (Caballero & Simsek, 2020). In the context of agricultural startups in Uganda, the relevance of the Risk-Centric Budgeting Theory becomes evident. Agriculture is inherently susceptible to numerous risks, including weather fluctuations, pests, market volatility, and policy changes and moreover land tenure disputes (Locke, 2012); (Nauges and Chavas, 2020); (Borodin. Bourtembourg & Labadie, 2016).

By applying a risk-centric budgeting approach, these startups can proactively address and manage these uncertainties. This would not only enhance the resilience of agricultural startups

but also contribute to more stable and predictable financial outcomes (Caballero & Simsek, 2020).

However, it is essential to consider potential counterarguments and challenges associated with implementing this method in agricultural startups in Uganda. One challenge is the availability of data and expertise required for a comprehensive risk assessment as highlighted by (Xenidis and Stavrakas, 2012). Many agricultural startups in Uganda may lack access to historical data or the necessary analytical skills to quantify risks accurately (USBSU, 2015). Therefore, To maximize the benefits of this method while reducing any negatives, leveraging modern technology would be ideal for ASBs in data analytics (Coble et al, 2018).

2.5 FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

Financial performance is an indicator of a company's overall financial well-being during a given time period as assessed by capital adequacy, liquidity, solvency, efficiency, leverage, and profitability (Fatihudin and Mochilas, 2018). In Short, to achieve these financial aspects, start-ups must have the ability to manage and govern their own resources (Tudose et al., 2022). In their review of financial performance of star-ups, Narian (2021) noted that cash flow issues were the cause of the 82% failure rate in 2018.

Moreover, Jianru, Yitong & Jian (2020) in their review, they noted deficiencies in capital planning, inefficient resource allocation, lack of capital management all which have a direct hindrance to the firm's profitability and performance in general. Moreso, they noted lack of financial management experience by the owners of start-ups. The researcher also established that poor budgeting and poor financial management in general are major problems that face. They therefore noted a need for start-ups to analyze their financial activities if they determine the final profit or loss. Budgeting is ideal in this case to create a detailed plan of expected income and expenses. Here, start-ups can allocate funds for various aspects of their operations. As a result, they are able to anticipate their costs and thus plan accordingly.

In another study, Gupta and Jain (2016) examined capital budgeting practices among start-up businesses in Haryana. Their results indicated that only 12.5% of small businesses registered as private/public prepared capital budgets. However the researcher highlights that most

businesses in the 12.5% did not make proper budgets. Jianru, Jian and Yitong (2020) highlight that in the absence of well laid/accurate budgets, startups are at the risk of over spending. They may lack a clear understanding of their financial limits thus engaging expenditures that strain their financial resources. Gupta and Jain (2016) also noted that 80% of startups created budgets based on project priorities. Nauges and Chavas (2020) highlights risks associated with prioritization of activities. This approach limits broader investment hence may cause businesses to miss out on profitable opportunities that fall outside the scope of their priorities (Nauges and Chavas, 2020); (Borodin, Bourtembourg & Labadie, 2016).

In addition to the preceding findings, Zhang (2023) claims that budgeting can discover financial deficits and surpluses. In other words, startups can detect financial imbalances and take corrective action (Naluwugge & Sserwanga, 2018). According to Matovu and Kyeyune (2016), these start-ups may foresee financial surpluses or deficits by projecting income and expenses, which is useful in the context of seasonal farming cycles. Furthermore, Naluwugge and Sserwanga (2018) emphasize that budgeting enables agricultural entrepreneurs to actively manage their resources, whether they anticipate surpluses that may be spent in developing operations or shortfalls that necessitate cost-cutting measures. This supports Zhang's assertion that financial imbalances in agricultural start-up firms should be detected and corrected.

However Mashau and Makhunga (2018) argue that Zhang's claim may lead to the risk of profitability emphasis which focuses on cost cutting measures especially in times of shortfalls. Here, startups might overlook broader social and environmental responsibilities. In agricultural startups, the pursuit of profitability, especially during financial constraints, may inadvertently lead to labor exploitation. The pressure to cut costs could manifest in inadequate labor practices, such as underpayment, unsafe working conditions, and irregular recruitment systems For example, a report by the (ILO) International Labor Organisation (2020), highlights that the agricultural sector is associated with labor exploitation and unruly recruitment systems as illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 5; labor exploitation and unlawful recruitment in agriculture 2020 -2022 (Source; (ILO), 2020)

For the case of Uganda where, Agricultural startups are characterized by limited resources, such problems of labor exploitation may arise with budgeting if the businessmen approach shortfalls by cost cutting (Nurcahyo, Akbar & Gabriel, 2018); (Lee, 2016).

The discussed studies highlight the gaps existing in the agricultural start-ups that authors believe effective budgeting could close. (Fatihudin and Mochilas, 2018) highlighted the inability to manage resources. Gupta and Jain (2016) highlighted the failure of start-ups to manage their capital yet this is crucial for the agricultural start-ups capital where capital is always limited as stated by (Nurcahyo, Akbar & Gabriel, 2018). Gupta and Jain (2016) also highlighted the problem of improper budgets or budgets with mistakes which arises from the lack of skills and limited knowledge of budgeting in start-ups.

2.6 CRITIQUE OF THE EXISTING LITERATURE;

The existing literature on the impact of budgeting strategies on financial performance raises interesting issues, but some essential topics must be addressed. To begin, it is critical to point out that some studies listed do not directly address the context of agricultural entrepreneurs in Uganda. Gupta and Jain (2016), for example, highlighted the lack of capital budgeting abilities among start-up enterprises in Kenya. They primarily focus on budgeting techniques in general or within specific nations such as Kenya, which may or may not be relevant to the unique issues faced by agricultural businesses in Uganda. As a result, there is a need for additional research into the budgeting methods and financial issues of startups in this environment.

Furthermore, the budgeting methods both in the categories of modern or traditional are generalized while in studies about their advantages and disadvantages. The challenges, resource requirements, and financial management needs of different sectors can be vastly different. For instance, what works for a tech startup might not be suitable for an agricultural startup. As a result, it's not entirely fair to assume that the results from studies in one sector can be directly applied to the agricultural sector.

In summary, while the theories and studies provide valuable insights into the role of budgeting in startup financial performance, it is crucial to emphasize the limitations of the existing studies in terms of their relevance to Uganda and the agricultural sector. More research that is context-specific and industry-specific is needed to provide a comprehensive understanding of how budgeting impacts the financial performance of startups in Uganda, particularly those in the agricultural sector. Finally, the current literature neglects an examination of the budgetary tools and leadership styles employed by these ASBs. This is an oversight that undermines a comprehensive understanding of the many other crucial factors influencing budgetary effectiveness.

The next chapter therefore discusses the methodology that will guide further research of this study.

3. METHODOLOGY

Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to explain the methodology employed to carry out the research of this study. According to Saunders et al., (2016); Punch (2014); Dissanayake (2023) and Raythana (2017), methodology is the fundamental framework outlining how a research study will be carried out. This definition emphasizes that methodology goes beyond mere research methods or techniques; it encompasses the broader philosophical and theoretical framework that informs the research design and decision-making.

Using the "research onion" concept developed by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill in (2019), this chapter will delve deeper into several key areas. It will start with a discussion of research philosophy, followed by research approach, strategy, choice, and techniques. Furthermore, the chapter will provide a critical examination of the methods used for data collection and analysis. Finally, it will conclude by addressing the ethical considerations and limitations of this research.

Figure 6; Research Methods for Business Students. (Source; Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019).

3.1 Research Philosophy;

According to Lewis and Thornhill (2019, p. 130) and Regina & Zukauskas (2015, p. 10), research philosophy revolves around the researcher's beliefs and assumptions regarding the generation of understanding. Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019) define research philosophy as having five major components: 1) Interpretivism, 2) Critical Realism, 3) Positivism, 2) Pragmatism, 4) Postmodernism, and 5) Postmodernism. In comparison to other philosophical methods, pragmatism provides a useful framework for integrating objective and subjective elements, including facts, values, and context-specific experiences (Morgan, 2014).

Pragmatists hold the view that the significance of knowledge resides in its capacity to effectively tackle real-world issues.(Rashid, 2023). Agriculture is a fundamental sector of Uganda employing at least 70% of the people and contributing approximately 26% of GDP (Jaramillo,2018); (Douglas et al., 2017; Dalberg, 2011). Therefore, the fall from start-ups due to financial failures pauses a significant insecurity in the country making it a 'real-world problem'. The research will adopt this approach to explore theories and concepts related to the practical impact of budgeting on financial performance (Saunders and Lewis, 2016).

3.1.1 Data collection Methods;

This research employs both quantitative and qualitative approaches using questionnaires and interviews to gather data. This is termed as mixed methods (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). For example, to understand the social and cultural context in which a research topic is embedded, a qualitative method is employed, while to explore numeric information, a quantitative approach is the suit (Vivek, 2022).

One disadvantage of mixed methods research is the possible unease of reconciling qualitative and quantitative data, incase data is collected at varying times (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Furthermore, mixed methods consume a lot of time and resources as it requires advanced proficiency and meticulous organization (Onwuegbuzie & Collins, 2018). However, these

criticisms do not apply to this particular study, since the researcher has had enough time of 7 months to collect data yet with sufficient resources such as school support.

3.2 Research Approach;

The two common approaches including inductive and deductive have successfully been used by numerous authors in their studies; (Gioia, Corley and Hamilton, 2013); (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). However in this research, the inductive approach is applied. This is because In the inductive approach, researchers gather data and information from their observations and analysis to develop theories or generalizations based on this data. Compared to the deductive approach, where researchers start with a specific theory or hypothesis and collect data to test it (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The presence of gaps in the already existing research creates a definite need to gain a better understanding of why the (ASBs) Agricultural Start-up businesses face financial dilemmas in the presence of budgetary solutions. According to Weinstein (2009), Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2019), the inductive approach offers the flexibility that allows adaptation to real-world research needs for solving real- world problems. Hence, making it a better approach for this research than deductive.

3.3 Research Strategy

The researcher prepared a questionnaire with a mix of closed and open-ended questions, targeting key financial aspects, budgeting methods, and the impact on financial performance. Moreover, questionnaires are suitable for collecting data from a relatively large sample size (Dalato and Gomezi, 2018). You can distribute questionnaires to numerous participants simultaneously, making it a time-effective method (Dalato and Gomezi, 2018)

Moreso, the researcher, selected the 27 agricultural start-up businesses, considering factors like size, location, and budgeting practices to ensure diversity in the sample. The prepared questionnaires were given to the selected businesses, together with a cover letter outlining the research's goal and requesting their participation. During the same time period, the researcher conducted interviews with 3 important stakeholders. These interviews enabled a more in-depth examination of budgeting approaches and their practical implications.

3.4 Data Collection and Analysis

In this research, convenience sampling was employed to select respondents. Here, the target population is chosen based on practical considerations like accessibility, proximity, availability, or willingness to participate (Golzar, Noah and Tajik, 2022). This sampling method offers several advantages, such as cost-effectiveness, time efficiency, and simplicity in implementation (Shorten & Moorley, 2014). However, when dealing with hard-to-reach or populations, probability sampling may not suffice as a suitable method (Berndt, 2020). Nonetheless, for the case of this matter, convenient sampling was suitable as ASBs are numerous in Uganda making at least 50 % of the existing start-ups. It was therefore easy for the researcher to gain respondents to both interviews and questionnaires.

To analyze the interview findings, the researcher analyzed questionnaire and interview data thematically to find how budgeting has affected financial performance indicators, such as cash flows and resource allocation. Through thematic analysis, recurring themes and patterns related to budgeting practices and financial performance were identified.

The findings from both the questionnaires and interviews were integrated to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research topic. To ensure the reliability and validity of the results, I compared the quantitative findings with the qualitative insights and the literature review to find if they aligned or revealed any disparities. Finally, the researcher compiled the research findings into a comprehensive report, drawing conclusions about the impact of budgeting methods on the financial performance of agricultural start-up businesses in Uganda.

3.5 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS;

Research ethics, as defined by Soundararajan et al. (2022), encompass aspects such as societal respect and responsible utilization of resources. Throughout this research, a paramount ethical consideration revolved around the prevention of plagiarism. As restricted by Soundararajan et al. (2022), plagiarism limits researchers from critical thinking hence shallow

research which does not provide satisfying results. Furthermore, the researcher diligently safeguarded the well-being of the participants, including the preservation of their identity, dignity, and values Hasan et al. (2021).

In the pursuit of ethical research, cognitive access was established by engaging with the managerial team to obtain participants' informed consent, coupled with an acknowledgment of their right to withdraw consent at any point. Consent forms explicitly outlined data protection measures, such as secure password-protected storage disks, as underscored by Saunders and Thornhill (2019). This approach not only fosters trust and acceptance among participants but also mitigates potential conflicts and biases, as Oswald (2021) emphasizes the preservation of participant anonymity.

Furthermore, participants were comprehensively informed that the research sought to catalyze a positive impact on the financial performance of agricultural startups. This transparency, aligning with the tenets of Saunders and Thornhill (2019), enhances organizational cooperation, particularly when research objectives hold the promise of favorable outcomes.

3.6 LIMITATIONS

The main limitation during this research regards restricted data access of certain aspects which respondents considered as confidential. This included financial reports of their businesses which limited the acquisition of specific alterations in their annual budget figures. Thus information that regards financial performance such as expenses and profit in exact figures was unavailable. Limited access to specific data can impact the internal validity of the research. The inability to verify financial reports directly may introduce measurement errors and affect the overall validity of the research finding (Politano, Walton, & Roberts, 2017); (Brooks, 2018).

Moreso, some of the interviews for this study were conducted through online platforms such as whatsapp. Online interviews are susceptible to technical glitches like poor internet connectivity, dropped calls, or disruptions, which can disrupt the flow of the interview and affect data quality (Hampton et al.,2020).

Furthermore, conducting interviews in person has the benefit of creating a strong connection between the researcher and the respondents (Meijer et al., 2021). Geiselman et al. (1984),

whose work is cited by Meijer et al. (2021), argued that this strong connection is vital as it puts interviewees at ease. As a result, they are more likely to have open and honest conversations with the interviewer.

3.7 CONCLUSION;

Applying Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill's (2019) "research onion" framework, this chapter elucidated the research philosophy, strategy, approach, data collection and analysis methods employed in this study. A summarized overview of the methodology is presented in Table 3.7

Table 1; Summary of methodology;

Philosophy		Pragmatism
Approach		Induction
Methods		Quantitative and qualitative
Strategy		questionnaires and Interviews
Analysis		Visualization and transcribing

Source (Researcher's construction construction)

The following chapter will focus on revealing the findings from questionnaires and interviews, as well as comparing them to the preceding findings in the literature review.

CHAPTER 4;

FINDINGS

4.1. Introduction

The role of this chapter in this study is to present and analyze findings from the primary data that were achieved with a mixed method approach. This study will explore the budgetary methods (traditional or modern) and tools employed by these ASBS. By evaluating their current budgeting methods and tools, the study aims to identify opportunities for enhancing the financial performance of these agricultural start-ups through better budgeting practices. This chapter will more so analyze the specific dilemmas faced by agricultural start-ups in Uganda resulting from inadequate financial planning/budgeting. Furthermore, the barriers of efficient budgeting will be explored to understand the problems encountered by these start-up businesses as they attempt to implement budgeting.

4.2. Respondents that Consented to Biography display.

Name	Firm name	position	Length of service
Alvin Mbabazi	Batuma Dairy farm	Accountant	3 years
Jean	Farm to table	Founder and Manager	1-5 years
Kananura Benson	NARO/ National Agric research Organization	Information and technology budget department	5 years
Nkusi Gerald	Adventure Afrika	Founder	2 years
Akandwanaho Edwin	Munakyalo Agro-fresh	secretary	4 years
The Asset	Uzima chicken	Founder	6 years
Atuheire Elizabeth	Kituzi center-Kyanamira	secretary	1 year
Nyinomuhangrebecca	Kachwekano potato growers	founder	3 years
Kiconco Phiona	Shamba Nzuri ltd	_____	_____
Charles busuugwa	Avo Agroecology ltd	Manager	2 years
Dennish Johnathan	Bingo fresh	_____	_____
Anonymous	_____	Foundeer	3years
Anonymmous	_____	_____	2yrs
Niwagaba Timothy	Kwanzi farm	Secretary	_____

Figure 7; Respondents Biography (Source; Researcher)

4. 3. Evaluating Budget presence rate in ASB

The researcher received a total of 27 responses from both questionnaires and interviews. At least 24 respondents confirmed that there was an active budgeting approach in their agricultural firms hence giving a total of 88.89%. Only 3 responded indicated a total absence of budgeting in their organizations hence making a percentage of 11.1% as indicated below in both calculations and figure 1.

Table 2; Budgeting rate in frequency and %

Budgeting	Frequency	Valid percentage
Present	24	88.89%
Absent	3	11.1%

Source; Researcher's Findings

Figure 8; Budgeting presence (Source; Researcher's findings)

The study's findings indicate that a significant proportion of start-up businesses use budgeting. However, a smaller number of start-ups do not prioritize budgeting. Their rationale for not budgeting is rooted in the perception that; 'their initial capital investment is limited, and their sales volume is also relatively low' In essence, these start-ups feel that the resource constraints and the scale of their operations do not warrant the structured financial planning and control that budgeting typically provides. They have thus adopted more informal or reactive approaches to financial management. These include taking notes of financial transactions in notebooks or

using the envelope method where cash is set aside for specific expenses of the day as a way to be strict on spending.

4.3.1 Analysis;

Start-ups that actively engage in budgeting are those that have experienced growth in size (Reddy and Mishra, 2018). In chapter 2, they have been identified as large scale Agri-startups (Kumbhat and Sshil, 2018);(Nurcahyo, Akbae & Gabriel, 2018); (Lee, 2016).

These expanding start-ups typically boast larger employee numbers and multiple activities that require active budgeting (Hung et al, 2018). Kumbhat and Sshil (2018); Hung et al, (2018) cited the presence of diverse operations, including multiple product lines, services, and departments, as a primary driver for their budgeting efforts. In their view, budgeting was an essential tool for efficiently allocating their abundant resources.

In contrast, smaller start-ups at the micro level, characterized by limited resources, were less inclined to adopt budgeting practices. Chapter 2 states that micro-start-ups employ a minimum of 5-49 employees (Andersen, 2012); (Greenbank, 2020). Moreover, while analyzing the findings some of the start-ups that didn't do budgeting were less than two years old. This justifies their less or no need for budgeting however, they also still face small financial dilemmas such as consistent disappearance of small funds.

Although these micro-start-ups complain of limited resources, budgeting is still needed by them since it is a powerful tool to help them expand funding and resources from investors (Redburn, 2017); (Cote, 2022). When they present well-structured budgets and financial plans, they are more likely to pull the focus of potential investors, demonstrating their seriousness and commitment to responsible financial management (Redburn, 2017); (Cote, 2022).

4.4 The impact of budgeting on financial performance

Respondents were given the options of Agreeing, Strongly agreeing, neutral, disagreeing and strongly disagreeing whether budgeting has played a great role in improving their financial performance.

Of the 24 start-ups that did budgeting, only two options were responded to where only 9 respondents agreed that budgeting had improved their financial performance especially through managing their expenditures on cost of production. The rest of the respondents (15) disagreed.

Table 3; Impact of budgeting on ASBs

Role of budgeting on financial improvement	Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
number	9	0	0	14	0

Source; Researcher's Findings

Respondents in agreement with the statement offered varied explanations in alignment with the literature review perspectives on how budgeting impacts the financial performance of Agricultural Startup Businesses (ASBs).

They emphasized the following key points:

4.4.1 Cost Management in Farming: One respondent stated that while budgeting , he is able to estimate revenues and expenses for seeds, labor,and equipment such as hoes, pangas and slashers.

This resonates with chapter 2 which highlights that budgeting empowers farmers to allocate their resources judiciously, pinpointing opportunities for cost minimization while preserving productivity and efficiency. Through meticulous expense tracking, farmers can detect inefficiencies, refine their operations, and enhance the efficiency of their production processes (Santos, 2017).

4.4.2 Generating Income and Boosting Profits: One respondent who had acquired funding from (NAADS) National Agricultural Advisory services stated that '*annual budget was supposed to be attached on the application form*'. This resonates with the studies of Redburn (2017) & Cote (2022) which affirm that indeed well-structured budgets and financial plans are more likely to pull potential investors, demonstrating their seriousness and commitment to responsible financial management. Consequently, it enables well-informed choices regarding investments, loans, and marketing endeavors, all aimed at optimizing profitability.

4.4.3 Transparency and Accountability: Another respondent highlighted that Budgets establish clear financial expectations and allocate resources for specific activities. This transparency makes it more challenging for unfaithful stakeholders to manipulate funds discreetly. When expenses and income are meticulously documented, any discrepancies become evident during budget reviews, promoting accountability. This control ensures that cash is used efficiently, avoiding unnecessary cash outflows.

During interviews, respondents mentioned that while budgeting helped with cash flow management through resource allocation, it didn't significantly improve financial performance. They face other unrelated factors that negatively impact their finances. They suggested that addressing these root causes of financial failure should take priority rather than relying sole

4.5 Root cause of Financial failure

4.5.1 Lack Access to funding from financial institutions:

One respondent stated that, banks do not find it easy to give them loans since they are start-ups and the banks are not sure whether their startups will thrive enough to bring back the money. In that case, acquiring funding requires processes and documentation which consume time. Limited access to banking and financial services can hinder the growth of savings and investment opportunities, affecting one's overall financial health (Grilli and Colombo, 2017). This restricts the ability to invest effectively hence deterring the level of financial output or profit.

4.5.1.1 Analysis

Budgeting involves allocating available financial resources efficiently as argued by (Hall et. al, 2017); (Kavanagh et al., 2011) in the literature review. However, when individuals face challenges like limited access to banking and financial services, they may have insufficient resources to allocate effectively. This can lead to a situation where budgeting becomes an exercise in managing scarcity rather than optimizing resources.

While managing scarcity is essential for short-term financial stability and survival, it may not necessarily lead to financial growth and long-term prosperity (Adam, Arlemalm & Flodin, 2023). Budgeting primarily for survival focuses on meeting immediate needs, which is crucial but may

not allow for investment, savings, or wealth accumulation (Gigante, 2014); (Lee & Nguyen, 2021)

In relation to the literature review, misallocation of resources is one of the gaps faced in the agricultural start-up businesses however, according to the findings, respondents believe that when the resources are limited, there is no need to spend time crafting budgets yet they can figure out their financial plans in their heads. While the respondents opinion may be right, notably, according to the literature review, budgeting is all about allocating resources but also optimizing their use. In situations with limited resources, effective budgeting becomes even more critical. By crafting a budget, startups can prioritize essential expenses, identify areas where cost-cutting is possible, and make the most efficient use of the available resources.

4.5.2 Political Instability

Some respondents highlighted the presidential succession conflicts of 2020 and 2021 where there was a desire to extend President Yoweri Museveni's rule beyond established term limits. They say that this chaos led to price fluctuations, which left them devastated with no morale to budget in a period that they have no control over.

4.5.2.1 Analysis;

In relation to the literature review that highlights the role of budgeting in mitigating risk, it is vital to consider the perspectives of the respondents which fall in critique of the Risk-Centric Budgeting Theory in light of their claim. Government decisions on taxes and pricing can have a substantial impact on the profitability of agricultural startups. In such cases, budgeting may not be sufficient to address the economic fallouts that are caused by government decisions which highly affect firms' financial performance (Osakwe and Moussa, 2017); (Moreira & Mehra, 2022).

In fact, one respondent gave a scenario during the political chaos where the government increased taxes on coffee exportation to boost revenue. He continued to highlight that this reduction not only lowered his net income from coffee sales but rather, the income of many more other coffee farmers in 2021.

The sudden increase in taxes and government-set pricing can disrupt their budgeting calculations. Farmers find it difficult to predict their income accurately, making it challenging to plan for expenses, investments, and loan repayments (Hedlund, 2019)

In relation to literature review, budgeting can be effective in managing internal risks; however, analysis from the findings shows that budgeting alone may not be sufficient for effective external risk mitigation such as government policies.

4.6 Evaluating Budgeting methods used;

Among the 23 respondents who confirmed active utilization of budgeting, they were presented with a choice regarding the specific budgeting methods they employed.

The breakdown of their selections revealed that 32% of the 23 respondents employed incremental budgeting, signifying adherence to the traditional approach as portrayed in the literature review. A minority of 19% opted for flexible budgeting, including both zero-based and activity-based budgeting methodologies. Additionally, 15% of respondents indicated the use of mixed methods, a selection contingent upon the specific contextual circumstances. Shockingly, 34% of respondents ticked the option of 'do not know'

Figure 9; Budgeting method employed In ASBs (Source; Researcher)

4.6.1 Analysis;

A respondent engaged in the production of climbing beans highlighted a specific instance during which a July drought resulted in a loss of more than 100 kilograms of beans due to scorching conditions.

The respondent emphasized that such situations challenge the applicability of incremental budgeting, as prices for agricultural products tend to fluctuate in response to variations in supply and demand. This resonates with arguments presented in chapter 2 where scholars such as Marcus (2015), Liyanagea, Gooneratnea (2021), and Atim and Elias (2017) critique traditional budgeting systems for their perceived inflexibility, particularly in the face of dynamic and unpredictable economic conditions.

Respondents who employed flexible budgeting methods highlighted its advantage in prioritizing and allocating resources based on specific activities. During interviews, one respondent emphasized that the head manager assumes the responsibility of identifying areas that require greater resource allocation than others which makes it easy and quick.

In contrast to the findings in the literature review, where scholars like Hall et al. (2017) and Kavanagh et al. (2011) advocate this top-down approach as the preferred method for resource allocation. However, it is vital to recognize that in such a hierarchical decision-making context, suggestions from front-line workers, including those involved in activities like plowing and weeding, may not receive due consideration (Cristobal and Diaz, 2018).

Front-line workers are uniquely positioned to identify opportunities for enhancing efficiency, introducing innovation, or implementing cost-saving measures (Charles, Francis and Oaya, 2021). The oversight of their input may lead to missed opportunities in the optimization of resource allocation. This could be another reason why start-ups continue to fail despite employing budgetary approaches. While centralized decision-making offers robust control mechanisms, decentralized leadership stands as a potent catalyst for innovation and agility, both of which are indispensable for the advancement and triumph of start-up ventures (Cristobal and Diaz, 2018); (Jan et al, 2017).

34% of the respondents indicated that they did not know the methods of budgeting and thus were not sure whether their approach is traditional or flexible. According to the researcher's analysis of this finding, it indicates that there is a budgetary knowledge gap among the ASBs.

Respondents who are unfamiliar with budgeting methods may overlook opportunities for cost-saving, revenue generation, or resource expansion that could enhance their financial performance. In today's contemporary society, people have a better chance of reaching their financial objectives if they possess the necessary financial planning knowledge (Tejero, Pilongo and Pamaran, 2015); (Paul and Saha, 2021).

The persistent failure of these agricultural start-ups in the face of financial dilemmas, such as cash flow and resource mismanagement, can be attributed to this critical knowledge gap as demonstrated in Chapter 2 by (Sullivan, 2017) and (BHRRC, 2023). The literature review underscored the issue of improper capital budgets. These findings starkly justify the assertion that these agricultural start-ups might not possess proper budgets simply because they lack the understanding of what type of budgeting they are employing.

4.7 BUDGETING TOOLS

The researcher moreso, investigated the budgeting tools employed by the Agricultural start-ups and the the results are represented in the table below. This investigation aims to understand how the tools of budgeting impact the effectiveness of the budgetary approach.

Table 4; Budgeting tools Frequency and Percentage

Tools	Frequency	Percentage
Excel	2	8%
Google sheets	3	13%
Colored coded files	13	43%
Paper cash templates	7	29%

Source; Researcher's Findings

Figure 10. Budgeting tool employed by ASBs (Source; Researcher)

In chapter 2, Jianru, Jian & Yitong (2020) highlight that most businesses in the 12.5% did not make proper budgets. highlights that in the absence of well laid/accurate budgets, startups are at the risk of over spending. The need to identify what tools these start-ups use was to investigate whether they could also be the lead to improper budgets. These same issues were confirmed in the findings where 43% of the ASBs in Uganda use color coded files as the meaning of budgeting. This process involves drawing columns and rows on paper sheets, then listing down the expected expenditure including transportation, rent, seed cost, electricity and water bills etc. The least utilized tools according to the questionnaire were excel and google sheets giving 8% and 13% respectively.

4.7.1 Analysis;

Having budgeting that involves paperwork counting the highest percentages of 29% and 43%, it raised the researcher's curiosity to understand the reason for this dominance. Some of the reasons stated included affordability and low complexity. However, other respondents highlighted the negatives of these tools. Firstly, physical files and notebooks are susceptible to damage, loss, or wear and tear, potentially leading to data loss and inaccuracies. They lack the data security and backup features that digital tools provide. Secondly, manual record-keeping is

time-consuming and prone to errors during data entry, calculations, and updates. In contrast, Excel can automate calculations and perform data validation, reducing the risk of errors (Mistoslav & Nataliya, 2016). Additionally, digital tools offer the advantage of easy data retrieval, searching, and sorting, making it simpler to analyze and report financial information (Lobodina & Lopushniak et al., 2020). Excel also allows for the easy generation of charts, graphs, and reports for better visualization of financial data (Lobodina & Lopushniak et al., 2020).

However, one thing that respondents said in relation to the inefficiency of excel and spreadsheets was that they require an initial investment, skills and reliable internet access yet they do not have enough capital to fund these. Therefore, Even though chapter 2 highlighted other causes of budget inefficiency in start-ups of different countries, It is important to note that for the case of Uganda, use of inefficient/traditional budgetary tools is one of the causes for budgetary failures. Therefore, there is a need for them to adopt the evolving technology, however, they must first acquire skills to use such softwares and yet they need access to boosters such as electricity and internet.

4.8 Summary

This chapter aimed at critically understanding the findings of this research.

The study found that a significant proportion of ASBs in Uganda engage in budgeting as a financial planning and management approach. Approximately 88.89% of respondents confirmed the active presence of budgeting in their organizations. However, a minority of 11.1% indicated the absence of budgeting in their firms, primarily due to resource limitations and low sales volumes.

Among ASBs that employed budgeting, various methods were used. Traditional incremental budgeting was the preferred choice for 32% of respondents, while flexible budgeting, including zero-based and activity-based methods, was chosen by 19%. Additionally, 15% of respondents utilized mixed methods, and 34% did not know the existing budgeting methods.

Moreso, respondents had mixed opinions regarding the impact of budgeting on their financial performance. (37.5%) agreed that budgeting had improved their financial performance, mainly through effective cost management in farming and income generation. However, a significant number of respondents (62.5%) disagreed with the statement, suggesting that budgeting alone might not be sufficient to address the financial challenges faced by ASBs. Respondents instead

highlighted other factors like political chaos and limits to funding that should be curbed first in order for budgeting to be effective.

The study explored the budgeting tools employed by ASBs. Surprisingly, 42.8% of respondents used color-coded files, and paper cash templates, a traditional and less efficient approach. Only 12.5% used Google Sheets, and 8.33% used Excel. Respondents who used digital tools like Excel and Google Sheets emphasized their efficiency and advantages over traditional paper-based methods. However, respondents noted that the adoption of digital tools required an initial investment, skills, and reliable internet access and thus could not manage to take it up.

4.9 Conclusion

The study reveals that budgeting is prevalent among ASBs in Uganda, but its impact on financial performance is a subject of debate. The findings underscore the need for better access to financial services and the challenges posed by political instability. Moreover, there is a gap in adopting modern digital tools, which is significantly lowering the efficiency and accuracy of budgeting processes. Having unveiled the insights collected in this chapter, it becomes paramount to derive conclusions and recommendations aligned with the objectives of this study in the next chapter.

CHAPTER FIVE

DEDUCTIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5. INTRODUCTION;

This chapter derives conclusions and recommendations grounded in the study's findings. Each objective will be assessed to determine the extent to which the research has achieved its goals. Section 5.3, will detail recommendations drawing from the findings. More so, section 5.4 will elaborate on the study's strong points. Finally, section 5.5 will address the research study's constraints and suggest areas for future research that could enhance the research study's findings.

5.1 Objective 1;

Role of budgeting on financial performance;

As analyzed through chapter 2 and 4, budgeting plays a pivotal role in resource allocation, risk mitigation, and ensuring accountability within ASBs.

However, it is crucial to acknowledge that financial performance in agricultural start-ups depends on a complex interplay of various factors beyond budgeting alone. These elements encompass efficient production techniques, effective marketing and distribution strategies, adaptability to weather and market fluctuations, and adherence to ethical and sustainable practices.

Furthermore, sound financial management and the ability to access funding sources are pivotal in ensuring that budgeting efforts translate into tangible financial performance. Additionally, the external environment, such as government policies, taxation, and pricing decisions, can significantly impact the financial stability of agricultural start-ups. Therefore, while budgeting serves as a fundamental tool for financial planning and resource allocation, it must be complemented by a holistic approach that addresses all these multifaceted components to attain and sustain financial success in the agricultural start-up landscape.

5.2 Assessing the existing budgeting practices

According to the findings, the majority of the startups are aware and have adopted budgeting methods both traditional and flexible. However it was noted that the majority of the number could not tell the budget type employed. This suggests that while budgeting is prevalent among startups, there may be some confusion or lack of clarity regarding budgeting. If startups are unclear about the methods they are using, they may not fully leverage the benefits of budgeting. This lack of understanding might result in less effective budgeting practices, potentially leading to resource misallocation and inefficient financial management.

The findings reveal that a significant majority of these startups are still entrenched in traditional budgeting approaches. However, the agricultural industry's ever-evolving nature requires the adaptability. This adaptability allows them to seamlessly transition between budgeting approaches as circumstances demand. In such a dynamic environment, flexibility is not just an advantage but a strategic necessity, enabling startups to optimize resource allocation, respond to market shifts, and seize opportunities efficiently.

5.3 To explore the barriers and obstacles that agricultural start-ups encounter when attempting to adopt and implement budgeting practices.

Chapter 2 highlighted lack of budgeting skills as a significant challenge faced by agricultural startups. Most startups have not immersed themselves in the growing technology for example the use of excel and google sheets which are reliable, accurate and time efficient.

Findings unveil a more complex situation in Uganda where the local budgeting tools are common. They involve paperwork such as colored file recording and paper cash templates which are used by the biggest percentage of farmers.

These methods are inefficient as the data is incurred and cannot be stored for so long. Moreover, budgeting based on manual structure can be full of mistakes hence being a reason why improper budgets exist. Several authors including Jianru, Yitong & Jian (2020) highlight that inefficient budgets lead to inaccurate determined losses or profits and hence there may arise misallocation of resources, directing funds to the wrong areas. This can result in decreased productivity and efficiency, ultimately affecting profitability.

The findings reveal that alongside the lack of budgeting skills among startups in Uganda, there is a prevailing issue of centralized decision-making in the budgetary process. In these startup businesses, budgetary decisions are typically made by top stakeholders, such as the manager, which can result in exclusion of valuable insights from front-line workers who have a deeper understanding of day-to-day operations. This relates to the literature review which highlights that start-ups are associated with excluding low line workers in budgetary decisions. This approach may overlook opportunities for cost reduction, efficiency improvement, and innovation that could enhance budgeting effectiveness.

In addition, it is notable that these emerging agricultural startups often face limitations in accessing funding. This constraint has led to a perception that budgeting is less of a priority. While the need to ignore the significance of budgeting in resource-constrained contexts is understandable, it is imperative to acknowledge that even in situations of resource scarcity, budgeting acts as a financial planning strategy to acquire resources from investors. The budgeting approach within the landscape of Ugandan agricultural startups, as portrayed by this research, stands as both relevant and pressing. It has the capacity to unlock prospects within an environment where resources are restricted.

5.4. Developing practical guidelines and recommendations

5.4.1 Invest in Budgeting Literacy and Modern Tools:

Agricultural start-up businesses should acquire training through schools or budgeting professionals to enhance budgeting skills among their team members. Encourage them to become proficient in modern budgeting tools like Excel or Google Sheets, which can streamline the budgeting process, reduce errors, and provide more accurate financial insights. This will help overcome the barrier of inefficient budgeting practices and improve the accuracy of their budgets. Furthermore, it is imperative for (ASBS) to engage employees with qualified budgetary skills. Achieving this objective entails implementing a robust hiring process which will help identify such personnels.

5.4.2 Implement Stakeholder Theory:

Utilizing the stakeholder theory as a guiding framework in their decision-making processes will help in including all stakeholder interests and engage with them to build strong budgets that tackle all aspects of their businesses.

Moreso, ASBs should stay attuned to stakeholder feedback and adapt their budgets accordingly. This better positions them to respond to market fluctuations and seize new opportunities, ultimately improving financial performance as noted in chapter 4

5.5.3 Diversify Funding Sources:

Given the constraints startups face in accessing funding, ASBs should explore various funding sources, including grants, partnerships, and microloans tailored for the agricultural sector. Diversifying their funding sources can provide more financial flexibility, making it easier to

allocate resources effectively and implement budgetary plans. This can help mitigate the perception that budgeting is less of a priority due to limited resources.

5.4.4 Promote Flexibility and Adaptability:

ASBs should Emphasize the importance of flexibility in budgeting. Encourage startups to adopt a more adaptable approach by combining traditional and modern budgeting methods. This flexibility allows them to respond effectively to the agricultural industry's ever-changing landscape. According to the findings, ASBs that seamlessly transition between budgeting approaches based on evolving circumstances are better equipped to optimize resource allocation, respond to market shifts, and capitalize on emerging opportunities.

5.5 Strengths of the Study

This research study contributes significantly to existing theory by reaffirming established concepts from the literature review. Employing a mixed-method research design, the study examined the role of budgeting in Uganda agricultural startups, the challenges they encountered, and potential mitigation strategies.

Notably, the research addresses critical gaps in the current literature. Contrary to assumptions made in the literature review, the study uncovers the reality that not all startups are well-versed in budgetary approaches. Moreover, it offers insights into the specific reasons behind budgetary inefficiencies in Ugandan agricultural startups.

Furthermore, the study refines the understanding of financial performance determinants. While the literature review tends to emphasize the positive impact of budgeting on financial outcomes, the study emphasizes that financial success is contingent on various factors, including leadership, market strategies, political stability, and overall sales efficacy. This nuanced perspective offers a more comprehensive view of the elements influencing financial performance.

5.6 Limitations and Areas for Future Research

One notable limitation of this study pertains to the sample size, which consisted of only 27 respondents. Formulating universally applicable recommendations for a country as populous and diverse as Uganda, with approximately 45.8 million inhabitants, based on such a limited sample, may not be entirely representative. Future research endeavors in this domain should endeavor to employ larger and more diverse samples, encompassing a broader spectrum of agricultural stakeholders.

Moreover, agriculture is an inherently multifaceted sector, embracing a wide array of business types and entities. While this research predominantly delved into the issues confronted by farmers, it is imperative to acknowledge that there exist numerous businesses indirectly associated with agriculture. These include agricultural equipment manufacturers, agribusiness consultants, and logistics providers specializing in agricultural services. These entities face distinct challenges and opportunities that necessitate separate investigations. Therefore, future research should delve deeper into micro-level units within the agricultural sector, ensuring a more comprehensive understanding that extends beyond the scope of farming and encompasses the entire spectrum of businesses contributing to this dynamic industry. Such nuanced research can offer valuable insights and tailored recommendations for each segment of the agricultural landscape.

Finally, after delving into the complex nature of agricultural startup enterprises in this detailed 10,000-word dissertation, it is evident that efficient budgetary procedures are critical to their success and sustainability. The findings highlight the critical role that besides budgeting, other stakeholders play in affecting the agricultural sector's financial performance. Thus, it is imperative for entrepreneurs, legislators, and stakeholders to all work together to create an environment that promotes budgetary techniques and allows for greater financial control efficiency. Our agricultural landscape's sustainability is dependent on the concrete efforts we take today to strengthen the financial foundations of our young agribusinesses.

REFERENCES;

Arora, A. (2021) 'The Fail-Safe Startup: Your Roadmap for Entrepreneurial Success', *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 35(4) Pages 656-658. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/08276331.2021.1982605>.

Anitah, A. (2022) 'The impact of financial literacy on the financial performance of trade and commerce small and medium enterprises in Uganda' : Busitema University. Available at; <https://ir.busitema.ac.ug/handle/20.500.12283/1653> [Accessed 13 Oct. 2023].

Anessi-Pessina, E. (2020) 'Reconsidering public budgeting after the COVID-19 outbreak: key lessons and future challenges', *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting & Financial Management*, 32(5)pp. 957-965. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPBAFM-07-2020-0115>

Andersén, J. (2012) 'A resource-based taxonomy of manufacturing MSMEs', *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research* 18, 98–122.

Ayo, S. et al. (2012) 'Agricultural pest control programmes, food security and safety', *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development*, 12(5), pp.6582–6592. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4314/ajfand.v12i5..>

Abdullahi, S. R. (2011) *Mastering cost and management accounting* (1st ed). Kano-Nigeria: Gidan Dabino Publishers

Authors: Adam, B. Årlemalm, S.C. & Flodin, F. (2023) 'Surviving Resource Scarcity', Bachelor Thesis in Business Administration'. Available at: <https://hj.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1763484/FULLTEXT01.pdf> [Accessed 27th, 10 2023].

Al-ddin, A.E.S. (2021) 'The strengths and weaknesses of the zero based budgeting system: future agenda'. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354076855_the_strengths_and_weaknesses_of_the_zero_based_budgeting_system_future_agenda [Available; 23rd 08 2023]

Bangomini, G. et al., (2015) 'Financial Inclusion in Rural Uganda: Testing Interaction Effect of Financial Literacy and Networks', *Journal of Africa Business*. Pp. 106-128 . <https://doi.org/10.1080/15228916.2016.1117382>

Borodin, V. (2016) 'Handling uncertainty in agricultural supply chain management: A state of the art' *European Journal of Operational Research*, 254(2), pp.348–359. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2016.03.057>.

Bairwa, S.L. (2014) 'Agripreneurship development as a tool to uplift agriculture', *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 4, 1–4.

Beredugo, S. B., Igbeng, E. I. & Eze, F. J. (2013) 'The Significance of International Corporate Governance Disclosures on Financial Reporting in Nigeria', *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(8), 1833-8119.

Baird, G.M. (2018) 'Water Main Criticality Scoring and GIS Centric Risk Mitigation: Applying GIS Spatial Analysis Tools and Apps for Greater Insight for High Risk Underground Infrastructure. Pipelines 2018', doi:<https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784481653.014>.

Brooks, D. (2018) 'Limitations and Conclusions for data collection', Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324503977_Limitations_and_Conclusions_for_data_collection[Accessed; 20 10 2023]

Berndt, A. E. (2020) 'Sampling methods', *Journal of Human Lactation*, 36(2), 224-226. DOI: 10.1177/0890334420906850

Cote, C. (2022) 'Why Is Budgeting Important in Business? 5 Reasons', Harvard Business School Online. Available at: <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/importance-of-budgeting-in-business> [Accessed; 29th 10 2023]

Chodankar, N.R. et al., (2020) 'True Meaning of Pseudocapacitors and Their Performance Metrics: Asymmetric versus Hybrid Supercapacitors', 16(37), p.2002806. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202002806>.

Christon, A. (2019) 'Financial literacy and financial performance of small and medium sized enterprises in Uganda' Available at: [doi:https://kyuspace.kyu.ac.ug/xmlui/handle/20.500.12504/509](https://kyuspace.kyu.ac.ug/xmlui/handle/20.500.12504/509). [Accessed 12 7 076 2023].

Cristóbal, J.R.S. et al. (2018) 'An Analysis of the Main Project Organizational structures: Advantages, Disadvantages, and Factors Affecting Their Selection', *Procedia Computer Science*, 138, pp.791–798.

Creswell, J.W. (2017) *Research design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 3rd Edition

Creswell, J.W. & Clark, V.L.P. (2020) *Understanding research: A consumer's guide*. Pearson.

Choi, S.-K. et al., (2021) 'Innovation Capabilities and the Performance of Start-Ups in Korea: The Role of Government Support Policies. *Journal of entrepreneurship and business Sustainability*', 13(11), p.6009. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116009>.

Caballero, R.J. and Simsek, A. (2020) 'A Risk-Centric Model of Demand Recessions and Speculation*. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjaa008>.

Coble, K.H. et al. (2018) 'Big Data in Agriculture: A Challenge for the Future', *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*, 40(1), pp.79–96. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/aep/ppx056>.

Charles, M. Francis, F. and Oayo, T.C. et al (2021) 'Effect of Employee Involvement in Decision Making and Organization Productivity', *Archives of Business Research* 9(3):28-34
DOI:10.14738/abr.93.9848'

Douglas, J. et al., (2017) 'An Exploratory Study of Critical Success Factors for SMEs in Kenya An Exploratory Study of Critical Success Factors for SMEs in Kenya'.available online; <https://sites.les.univr.it/eisic/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/20-EISIC-Douglas-Douglas-Muturi-Ochieng.pdf> [Accesses 23 08 2023]

Dunk, A.S.(2014) 'Budgetary participation, agreement on evaluation criteria and managerial performance' *A research note. Accounting Organization and Society*, Vol.15 (3), pp. 171 – 178

Dissanayake, E.V.A. (2023) ' A Systematic Approach for Designing a Research Methodology', *Research Design and Qualitative Methodology in International Relations*,

Dalberg. (2011). Report on Support to SMEs in Developing Countries Through Financial Intermediaries. Copenhagen. 10.1109/ICEBEG.2011.5881298

Decker, R. (2014) 'The Role of Entrepreneurship in US Job Creation and Economic Dynamism', *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 28(3), pp.3–24. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.28.3.3>.

Dalati, S. and Gomez, M.J. (2018) 'Modernizing the Academic Teaching and Research Environment' *Surveys and Questionnaires*, (pp.175-186). DOI:10.1007/978-3-319-74173-4_10

Jaramillo, F.C. (2018) The agri-food system; World bank.12th edition. Available at;<https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/678231542382500879/pdf/132140-WP-P16820-2-UGANDAECOMICUPDATE.pdf>. [21 06 2023]

Etim, O. E & Elias, I. A. (2017) 'Traditional Budgeting in Today's Business Environment', *Journal of Applied Finance & Banking*, 7(3), pp. 111-120

Ekou, J. (2014) 'Diary marketing and production in Uganda', *African Journal of Agricultural Research Dairy production and marketing in Uganda*, 9(10), pp.881–888. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5897/AJAR2013.8470>.

Grilli, L. et al. (2017) 'Funding Gaps? Access to Bank Loans by High-Tech Start-Ups', *Small Business Economics* 29(1), pp. 25-46. DOI:10.1007/s11187-005-4067-0

Greenwood, C. R. G. et al. (2022) *Incremental Budgeting and the Assumption of Growth: The Experience of Local Government*. Routledge. 1st Edition.

Greebank, P. (2020) 'Micro-business start-ups: challenging normative decision making?', *Marketing Intelligence & Planning* 18(4), pp. 206-212, DOI:10.1108/02634500010333415

Goldstein, C.E. (2018) 'Ethical issues in pragmatic randomized controlled trials', *a review of the recent literature identifies gaps in ethical argumentation*. *BMC Medical Ethics*,19(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-018-0253-x>.

Gioia, D.A., Corley, K. and Hamilton, A. (2013) *Seeking Qualitative Rigor in Inductive Research: Notes on the Gioia Methodology Organizational Research Methods*. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1094428112452151> (Accessed: 19 10 2023).

Golzar, J. and Tajik, O. (2022) 'Convenience Sampling'. *International journal of education and language studies* 1(2), p.1.

Gupta, K.P. & Jain, V. (2016) 'Capital budgeting practices in SME'S: A study of selected enterprises of Haryana'. *International Journal of Commerce and Management Research*, 2(2), 75-79.

Hallic, M and Rakia,K.H (2013) 'Traditional budgeting, why does it persist?: A case study of Värmlandstrafik 2(39). Available;

<https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1690924&dswid=-4309> [Accessed; 14th 06 2023]

Henn, m. & Weinstein, M. (2009) *A Critical Introduction to Social Research*. 2nd ed. Los Angeles [u.a.]: SAGE.

Hampton, K.et al. (2020) 'Repercussions of Poor Broadband Connectivity for Students in Rural and Small Town Michigan', Available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3749644. [Accessed; 19 10 2023]

Hovarth, P. and Sauter, R. (2020) 'Why Budgeting Fails: One Management System Is Not Enough'. *Harvard business school publishing*, pp; 1-6[online] Available at: https://capitalizeconsulting.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/HBR_Why_Budgeting_Fails_112014.pdf.

Hasan, N. *et al.* (2021) 'Ethical Considerations In Research', *Journal of Nursing Research, Patient Safety and Practise*, 1(1), pp. 1–4. doi:10.55529/jnrpsp11.1.4.

Hedlund. A. (2018) 'How Do Taxes Affect Entrepreneurship, Innovation, and Productivity?', The center of growth and opportunity. [Available; https://aaronhedlund.github.io/policy/CGO_taxinnovation.pdf] [Accessed; 27th 10 2023]

Hung, W.-H. et al., (2018) 'Understanding the organizational critical activities of manufacturers in case studies', *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 185, p.00022. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1051/matecconf/201818500022>.

ILO. (2022) 'Three-year Plan to tackle labor exploitation and unlawful recruitment in agriculture'. Available at:https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---europe/---ro-geneva/---ilo-rome/documents/gener icdocument/wcms_766362.pdf. [Accessed 12th 07 2023],

Jianru, X. Yintong, G. and Jian, D. (2020) 'Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research', *International Conference on Humanities Science and Society Development*, 451. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>.

Kuschel, K. (2018) 'Women-Led Startups and Their Contribution to Job Creation', *FGF studies in small business and entrepreneurship*, pp.139–156. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-73509-2_7.

Kumbat, A. and Suhil, P. (2018) 'Development Stages and Scaling Issues of Startups', *Indian Institute of Technology Delhi*, (pp.3-15) DOI:[10.1007/978-981-10-8926-8_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-8926-8_1)

Kumareswaran, S. (2019). 'A Critical Analysis of the Zero-Based Budgeting. University of Wolverhampton'. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/49310639/A_Critical_Analysis_of_the_Zero_Based_Budgeting[Accessed; 13 07 2023]

Kavanagh, S. C. (2011) *Anatomy of a Priority Driven Budget Process*, GFOA's Research and Consulting Center.

Liyanage, T. and Gooneratne, T. (2021) 'From 'Traditional' Budgeting to 'Better' Budgeting: Navigating through 'Stability' and 'Change'', *Management Accounting Frontiers*, 4, pp.27–50. doi:<https://doi.org/10.52153/prj0725005>.

Lutz, C.S. (2018) 'Understanding barriers and predictors of maternal immunization: Identifying gaps through an exploratory literature review', *Vaccine*, 36(49), pp.7445–7455. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2018.10.046>.

Lobodina, H.Z. (2021) 'Inclusive budgeting: theoretical aspects, prerequisites and need for implementation in ukraine', *Financial and Credit Activity Problems of Theory and Practice* , 2 (33), 463–472. <https://doi.org/10.18371/fcaptp.v2i33.207201>

Land, M (2015) 'Agricultural drivers. Land Matrix Global Observatory' Available at: <http://www.landmatrix.org/en/get-the-idea/agricultural-drivers/> (accessed 15 07 2015)

Mbogo, M. et al., (2021) 'Effect of budgeting practices on financial performance of manufacturing small and medium enterprises in Nairobi county, Kenya', *journal of language, technology & entrepreneurship in africa*, 12(1).

Mashau, P. (2018) 'The effects of cost cutting measures to staff performance' University of KwaZulu-Natal. DOI:10.31920/2516-5305/2018/V15n4a6

Mitchell, D. (2021) 'A reflection of changing priorities? The reallocation impact of priority-based budgeting in US municipalities', *Public Budgeting & Finance*. 42(3) doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/pbaf.12310>.

Marcus, W. (2015) 'Better budgeting methods : a comparative effect analysis on traditional budgeting problems'. Available at: <https://repositorio.ucp.pt/handle/10400.14/18798>. [Accessed; 12 07 2023]

Meijer, E. et al. (2021) *Rapport Building: Online vs In-Person Interviews*, Maastricht University. Centre for Research and Evidence on Security Threats. Available at: https://crestresearch.ac.uk/download/3705/rapport_building_report-1.pdf (Accessed: 14 09 2023).

Morgan, D.L. & Yoder, J.H. (2019) 'Mixed methods research: A critique and a call to pluralism', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 13(2), 107-121.

Narian, S. (2021) 'How Early Financial Management can Benefit Startups'. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353614970_How_Early_Financial_Management_can_Benefit_Startups [Accessed; 14th 07 2023]

Němec, J. Vries, M. S. (2019) 'Effectuating Performance-Based Budgeting Takes Time. Governance and public management', pp.257–269. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-02077-4_14.

Nauges, C. and Chavas, J. (2020) 'Uncertainty, Learning, and Technology Adoption in Agriculture', *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*, 42(1), pp.42–53. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/aapp.13003>.

NSBS U. (2015) 'National-Small-Business-Survey-report', Available at: <https://www.nathaninc.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/National-Small-Business-Survey-report.pdf>. [Accessed 13th 07 2023]

Nurcahyo, R. (2018) 'Characteristics of startup company and its strategy: Analysis of Indonesia fashion startup companies', *University of Indonesia*, DOI:10.14419/ijet.v7i2.34.13908

Nguyen, L. and Lee, J. (2021) 'Manual Budgeting and Forecasting and Its Disadvantages', *International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development*, 3(1), pp.47–51.

Neszmely, G. Gally, S.E. (2019) 'The role of agriculture in the economic development of Mauritius' *Journal of agriculture in the economic development* , 63(5), pp.427-443. <https://ageconsearch.umn.edu/record/2>

Noui, M.E. and Dehane, M. (2023) 'Analysing Startups Failure Factors: Evidence from CB Insights Tech Market Intelligence Platform' *Journal of Economic Growth and Entrepreneurship JEGE Spatial and entrepreneurial development studies laboratory*, 6(1) pp:10-30

Ouassini, I. (2018) 'An Introduction to the Concept of Incremental Budgeting and Beyond Budgeting', *electric Journal*, DOI:10.2139/ssrn.3140059.

Onwuegbuzie, A.J. & Johnson, R.B. (2019) The validity issue in mixed research. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 13(1), 4-22

Oswaldo, L.-Q. (2021) 'Ethical Principles and Challenges for Qualitative Researchers', in *Computer Supported Qualitative Research. World Conference on Qualitative Research*. Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-70187-1_1 (Accessed: 12 10 2023).

Politano, P. M. Walton, R. O. & Roberts, D. L. (2017) Introduction to the Process of Research:Methodology Consideration. Charleston, South Carolina, USA: Hang Time Publishing, Ltd. Co

Pimpong, S. & Laryea, H. (2016) 'Budgeting and its impact on financial performance: the case of non-bank financial institutions in Ghana', *International Journal of Academic Research and Reflection*, 4 (5), 12-22.

Paul, S. and Saha, M. (2021) 'Impact on Education Budget on Literacy Rate BD'. Available at;https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351985927_5_Impact_on_Education_Budget_on_Literacy_Rate_BD_Accountant [Accessed; 25th 10 2023].

Gigante, P. J.O. (2014) 'Cash budget versus financial budget : advantages and disadvantages : a case study. Repositorio.ucp.pt', Available at: <https://repositorio.ucp.pt/handle/10400.14/17053> [Accessed; 22nd 10 2023]

Punch, K. 2014 *Introduction to Social Research. Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. 3rd ed. Sage.

Prajogo, D.I. (2016) 'The strategic fit between innovation strategies and business environment in delivering business performance', *International Journal of Production Economics*, 171(2), pp.241–249. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2015.07.037>

Rabie, C., Cant, M. C., & Wiid, J. A. (2016) 'Training and development in SMEs: South Africa's key to survival and success?', *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 32(4), 1009–1024. <https://doi.org/10.19030/jabr.v32i4.9717>

Redburn, S. (2017) 'A Series of Discussion Papers on Re-Imagining the Federal Budget Process Budgeting for Investment'. Available at: <https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/redburn-layout-final-pdf-3-6-17.pdf> [Accessed 2nd 11 2023].

Rosella, N. (2015) ' Role of innovation in creating a company's competitive advantage', *Ecoforum Journal (University of Suceava, Romania)*1(6).

Reddy, P. & Mishra, S. (2018) 'Budgeting and forecasting for multinational companies during covid'.

Available at; https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354906917_BUDGETING_AND_FORECASTING_FOR_MULTINATIONAL_COMPANIES_DURING_COVID [Accessed on;28th 10 2023]

Rovai, A.P., Baker, J.D. and Ponton, M.K. (2014) *Social Science Research Design and Statistics*. Chesapeake, VA: Watertree Press LLC.

Rashid, M.H.A. (2023) ' Research Philosophy: Positivism, Interpretivism, and Pragmatism'. Available at: <https://limbd.org/research-philosophy-positivism-interpretivism-and-pragmatism/>. [Accessed 22 09 2023]

Sauter, R. (2004) 'Why Budgeting Fails: One Management System Is Not Enough' *Harvard Business school publishing*. [online] Available at: https://capitalizeconsulting.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/HBR_Why_Budgeting_Fails_112014.pdf. [Accessed; 11 07 2023]

Santos, A.B. Mello, M.F. (2016) 'The importance of cost management in a manufacturing company of hydroelectric plants - a case study', *Brazilian Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 13(1), p.94. doi:<https://doi.org/10.14488/bjopm.2016.v13.n1.a11>.

Soundararajan, M. (2022) 'Ethics and Plagiarism: A Researcher's Perspective. DOI:10.37896/JBSV22.12/1552

Scott, J.K. and Enu-Kwesi, F. (2018) 'Role of Budgeting Practices in Service Delivery in the Public Sector: A Study of District Assemblies in Ghana', *Human Resource Management Research* 8(2), pp. 23-33. DOI: 10.5923/j.hrmr.20180802.01

Subbotina, K.E. and Субботина, К.Е. (2014) 'Modern approaches to budgeting as a method of financial control', *Journal of Economics and Social Sciences*, (5), p.4.

San, S. and Heng, R. (2011), *Management Accounting: A Focus on Decision Making*, United States. *Amity Journal of Strategic Management*, 1(2)

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2019) *Research Methods for Business Students*. 8th edn. New York: Pearson.

Shorten, A. & Moorley, C. (2014) 'Selecting the sample. Evidence Based Nursing', 17(2), 32–33
Tejero, E. 'Financial Literacy in Relation to Financial Management', *University of Bohol Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 7. DOI:10.15631/ub.mrj.v7i0.125

Tibeingana, A. (2019) 'Anecdotal Evidence of the Role of Incubation in the Growth of Business Start-Ups in Uganda. *International Business Research*, 13(1), p.64. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v13n1p64>.

Torraco, R.J. (2016) 'Writing Integrative Literature Reviews: using the past and present to explore the future', *Human Resource Development Review*, 15(4), pp.404–428. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484316671606>.

Verben, J. (2017) 'Small Business Taxation in Uganda Tax Compliance and Tax Culture among Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Kampala' *International Development Studies*.

Wolf, K. (2020) 'Why It's Time to Say Goodbye to Traditional Budgeting'. Available at;<https://www.amanet.org/articles/why-it-s-time-to-say-goodbye-to-traditional-budgeting/>[Access ed 15th 07 2023].

Vivek, R. (2022) Systematic review of modern techniques in qualitative research. *Management and Entrepreneurship Trends of Development*, 4(22), 34–49. <https://doi.org/10.26661/2522-1566/2022-4/22-03>

Zhang, L. (2023) 'The Role of Budgeting in Financial Control and Performance Evaluation', *International Journal of Accounting research*, 11(3). doi:<https://doi.org/10.35248/2472-114X.23.11.336>.

APPENDIX;

ETHICAL FORM

Glasgow Caledonian University Glasgow School
for Business and Society

Undergraduate/Taught Postgraduate Research Project Ethical
Consideration

EC5/2020

Glasgow Caledonian University
Glasgow School for Business and Society

Undergraduate/Taught Postgraduate Research Project
Ethical Consideration

Your Details
Name of Student: Kirabo Desire
Department: Business
Programme: Business Management
Academic Session: Trimester C
Supervisor: Soumish Dev
The Project
Project Title: THE EFFICIENCY OF BUDGETING IN IMPROVING FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF AGRICULTURAL START-UP BUSINESS IN UGANDA.
Main Aim of Study: To create individual and organizational learning concerning the role of budgeting and how agricultural start-ups in Uganda can implement budgeting practices efficiently in order to improve their financial performance.
Contact with Others
Will your project bring you into direct or indirect (e.g. via internet surveys) contact with other people?
Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
If you have clicked "No" sign the section below and submit <i>this page only</i> to your supervisor for countersigning, otherwise complete the remainder of the form.
Your Signature
Signature: <i>desire</i> Date submitted: 27 th 08 2023
Ethical Approval (To be completed by supervisor)

I have checked the above for accuracy and I am satisfied that the information provided is an accurate reflection of the intended study.

There are no ethical issues causing me concern: ✓

Signature: Date: 20-Sep-23

Research Par

Number of Research Participants in your study: 21

Who are the Research Participants? Start-up business owners and their financial managers

On the basis of which criteria have they been selected? Interviews

Where and how will you recruit them for your study? Uganda through observations

Where and how will data collection take place (location, by phone/internet, by post)?
Uganda, through physical and phone interviews

Will any of the Research Participants be minors (under 16 in Scotland, under 18 in the rest of the UK)?

Yes

No ✓

If you have clicked "Yes" please note the following:

You must read the further guidance available on the School's Ethics website

You will need to obtain a PVG Disclosure (<https://www.mygov.scot/pvg-scheme/>)

This Ethics form, to which a copy of the disclosure must be attached, will need to be countersigned by a member of the School's Ethics committee

Please click here to indicate that you have understood these requirements

Methods of Data Collection to be Employed

Paper-based questionnaire Yes ✓ No

Internet survey Yes ✓ No

Interviews Yes ✓ No

Focus Groups Yes No

Other (please specify):

If you wish to guarantee internet survey respondents anonymity you must follow the requirements laid out in the [Survey Monkey](#) document available on the School's Ethics website (if you are using internet survey software other than Survey Monkey follow the same procedures for that software): please click here to confirm that you have read this

Confidentiality

Requests for confidentiality can only be accepted on the understanding that the confidential material will not be included in the written report or dissertation. They cannot be accepted on the understanding that the report/dissertation itself will be confidential. British universities are public bodies and all research carried out at undergraduate/taught masters level is by definition available for public scrutiny.

Please click here to indicate that you understand the limits to confidentiality in relation to your research

Potential Participant Distress

Is there any possibility that any of the procedures in your study will cause discomfort, anxiety, stress or embarrassment for your participants?

Yes

No

If you have answered "Yes" please describe, explain and justify how you will seek to minimise upset to your participants:

Please indicate your response to the following questions and discuss your response with your supervisor

Will you provide an oral explanation of the project to the subject?

Yes No

Will you provide a written explanation of the project to the subject?

Yes No

Will you ask the research participants to complete a consent form?

Yes No

If you have clicked "Yes" to the above please attach a copy (drafts are acceptable at this stage).

If you are seeking **verbal consent** please provide a statement of how you will seek to gain this from your participants:

In the process of conducting my academic research/dissertation, I will seek verbal consent from participants by clearly explaining the purpose of the study, the nature of their involvement, and their rights, and then requesting their explicit agreement to take part in the research.

Will you explain to the participants that you are a student undertaking degree or masters level studies?

Yes No

Will you explain to the research participants that they may not benefit from your study?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Will you offer the research participants the opportunity to decline to take part?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Will you offer the research participants the opportunity to withdraw at any stage?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Will you offer anonymity?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Will you adhere to the provisions of the Data Protection Act 2018?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Please briefly explain how the DPA will be adhered to: (see https://www.gcu.ac.uk/dataprotection/)		
Yes, I am fully committed to complying with the regulations stipulated in the Data Protection Act 2018. My approach involves to offer anonymity, offer the research participants the opportunity to withdraw at any stage and the opportunity to decline to take part.		
Your Own Safety		
Are there any aspects of your project which might have implications for your own safety?		
Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
If you have clicked "Yes", please indicate how you propose to minimise any risk to yourself:		
Check List		
Please tick the supporting documents you are submitting along with this application		
Participants Explanation form	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
Consent form (draft acceptable)	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
Questionnaire/survey text (draft acceptable)	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
PVG Disclosure	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Your Signature	
Signature: <i>desire</i>	Date: 27 th 08 2023
Please also type name here: Kirabo Desire	
Ethical Approval (To be completed by supervisor)	
I have checked the above for accuracy and I am satisfied that the information provided is an accurate reflection of the intended study. I confirm that the form contains all the relevant information and that all supporting documentation is attached.	
There are no ethical issues causing me concern	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
The ethical issues raised by this project require further consideration	<input type="checkbox"/>
Signature:	Date: 20-Sep-23
Please also type name here:	
If you have clicked the second option please forward to your departmental representative on the School's Ethics committee for further consideration.	

Appendix 3; STUDENT PROJECT/DISSERTATION RECORD

Signed meeting Forms (Appendix B)

Dear Kirabo,
I hereby confirm having signed your meeting protocols:

- June 8th, 2023
- June 23rd, 2023
- July 29th, 2023
- August 22nd, 2023
- September 12th, 2023
- September 26th, 2023
- October 27th, 2023
- November 1st, 2023

Sincerely,
Signature
Soumish Dev

.....
Your name
.....
Supervisor.

Appendix B: Student Project/Dissertation Supervision**Record Date of meeting: 08 June-2023****Student:**

1. **Desire Kirabo**

Supervisor(s) present: Soumish Dev

Review of actions from the last supervisory meeting:

Topics discussed:

1. Changed the research location from Mauritius to Uganda
2. Revised the research aim

Identification of any issues:

- Is progress being made? Yes Are goals being met? Yes

Actions set for the next meeting:

1. Deep analysis of what extent are small scale farmers acquainted and learned about budgeting.

Additional activity: Overcoming the technical issue challenges.

Confirmation from student and supervisor**Student: Desire Kirabo****Date 09-June-2023****Supervisor: Soumish Dev****Date 09-June-2023****Please note:** Supervisory meetings can be conducted electronically or by phone, and agreement by email is accepted in lieu of signatures.**Completing the form:** Students should complete the form, adding their name and date to the Confirmation section, and forward to the supervisor(s) present. The Supervisor should add their name and date if in agreement, and retain this form as a formal record of meetings with the student.

Appendix B: Student Project/Dissertation Supervision

Date of meeting: 23 June-2023

Student:

1. Desire Kirabo

Supervisor(s) present: Soumish Dev

Review of actions from the last supervisory meeting:

Topics discussed:

- 1 The relevancy of budgeting to start-up owners that did not attain higher education
- 2 The relationship between theoretical review and literature review.

Identification of any issues:

- Is progress being made? Yes
- Are goals being met? Yes

Actions set for the next meeting:

- 1 Consider researching about the start-ups that do budgeting and those that do not.
- 2 Submit the first chapter by Tuesday 27th June.

Additional activity:

Confirmation from student and supervisor

Student: Desire Kirabo

Date 23-June-2023

Supervisor: Soumish Dev

Date 23-June-2023

Please note: Supervisory meetings can be conducted electronically or by phone, and agreement by email is accepted in lieu of signatures.

Completing the form: Students should complete the form, adding their name and date to the Confirmation section, and forward to the supervisor(s) present. The Supervisor should add their name and date if in agreement, and retain this form as a formal record of meetings with the student.

Appendix B: Student Project/Dissertation Supervision

Date of meeting: 29th July 2023

Student:

1. Desire Kirabo

Supervisor(s) present: Soumish Dev

Review of actions from the last supervisory meeting:

Topics discussed:

- 1 Corrections on chapter one
2. major aspects that need to be included in chapter 2.
3. Methodology major requirements

Identification of any issues:

- Is progress being made? Yes
- Are goals being met? Yes

Actions set for the next meeting:

- 1 Writing my abstract
- 2 adding some pictorial/ schematic statistical representation of some past trend/ pattern on agriculture industry in Uganda

Additional activity:

Confirmation from student and supervisor

Student: Desire Kirabo

Date 29th-July-2023

Supervisor: Soumish Dev

Date 29th -July-2023

Please note: Supervisory meetings can be conducted electronically or by phone, and agreement by email is accepted in lieu of signatures.

Completing the form: Students should complete the form, adding their name and date to the Confirmation section, and forward to the supervisor(s) present. The Supervisor should add their name and date if in agreement, and retain this form as a formal record of meetings with the student.

Appendix B: Student Project/Dissertation Supervision**Date of meeting: 12 Sept-2023****Student:****1. Desire Kirabo****Supervisor(s) present: Soumish Dev**

Review of actions from the last supervisory meeting:

Topics discussed:

- 1 Word count regulation
- 2 The relationship between empirical review and literature review.
 3. Budgetary theories
 4. Financial performance aspects

Identification of any issues:

- Is progress being made? Yes
- Are goals being met? Yes

Actions set for the next meeting:

- 1 Done with the literature review
- 2 Focusing on the methodology
- .

Additional activity:

Confirmation from student and supervisor**Student: Desire Kirabo****Date 12th Sept-2023****Supervisor: Soumish Dev****Date 12th Sept-2023****Please note:** Supervisory meetings can be conducted electronically or by phone, and agreement by email is accepted in lieu of signatures.**Completing the form:** Students should complete the form, adding their name and date to the Confirmation section, and forward to the supervisor(s) present. The Supervisor should add their name and date if in agreement, and retain this form as a formal record of meetings with the student.

Appendix B: Student Project/Dissertation Supervision

Date of meeting: 26th September-2023

Student:

1. Desire Kirabo

Supervisor(s) present: Soumish Dev

Review of actions from the last supervisory meeting:

Topics discussed:

- 1 The increase on the number of respondents for purposes of large data collected
- 2 The need to change from questionnaires to consented recorded interviews since the respondents are not efficient with writing on questionnaires.

Identification of any issues:

- Is progress being made? Yes
- Are goals being met? Yes

Actions set for the next meeting:

- 1 Having collected all the data from all respondents
- 2 The start of chapter 4.

Additional activity:

Confirmation from student and supervisor

Student: Desire Kirabo

26th September-2023

Supervisor: Soumish Dev

26th September-2023

Please note: Supervisory meetings can be conducted electronically or by phone, and agreement by email is accepted in lieu of signatures.

Completing the form: Students should complete the form, adding their name and date to the Confirmation section, and forward to the supervisor(s) present. The Supervisor should add their name and date if in agreement, and retain this form as a formal record of meetings with the student.

Appendix B: Student Project/Dissertation Supervision

Date of meeting: 27October-2023

Student:

1. Desire Kirabo

Supervisor(s) present: Soumish Dev

Review of actions from the last supervisory meeting:

Topics discussed:

- 1 Review of the current progress
2. Use of SPSS

Identification of any issues:

- Is progress being made? Yes
- Are goals being met? Yes

Actions set for the next meeting:

- 1 Submit the final draft on turnitin

Additional activity:

Confirmation from student and supervisor

Student: Desire Kirabo

27October-2023

Supervisor: Soumish Dev

27October-2023

Please note: Supervisory meetings can be conducted electronically or by phone, and agreement by email is accepted in lieu of signatures.

Completing the form: Students should complete the form, adding their name and date to the Confirmation section, and forward to the supervisor(s) present. The Supervisor should add their name and date if in agreement, and retain this form as a formal record of meetings with the student.

Appendix 4; QUESTIONNAIRE.

Student; Kirabo Desire

Student Supervisor; Soumish Dev

Student ID; s2110979

THE ROLE OF BUDGETING IN IMPROVING FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF AGRICULTURAL START-UP BUSINESS IN UGANDA.

Greetings, I am Kirabo Desire, in my last year of a Business Management degree at the African Leadership University in Mauritius. As part of my dissertation, I am now working on a research study. The primary goal of this study is to assess the efficacy of budgeting in improving the financial performance of agricultural start-up firms in Uganda. The study project aims to get a deeper understanding of the existing budgeting techniques and tools used by these start-up businesses, assess their strengths and flaws, and recommend areas for future improvement.

Furthermore, this questionnaire aims to gather your thoughts on whether you believe budgeting has favorably impacted the financial performance of your startup, as well as the reasons behind your position. Your important views will be critical in developing practical guidelines and recommendations that are customized to the unique environment of agricultural start-ups in Uganda.

Your participation in completing this questionnaire is entirely voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw at any time without explanation. Rest assured that your responses will be treated with strict confidentiality, and you are under no need to divulge your name or the name of your startup if you do not like to.

It is estimated that completing this questionnaire will take about five minutes.

4

Consent:

I certify that I have read and understood the information presented above.

Yes/No

I am aware that my participation in completing this questionnaire is totally optional, and I reserve the right to withdraw at any moment and without explanation.

Yes/No

Thank you for your involvement and time.

Section 1:

Demographic Information In this section, we aim to ensure that our survey sample is cross-representative and provides a holistic approach to our research project.

1. Name:
2. How long have you been involved in the agricultural sector in Uganda? (Tick where applicable)

- 1-5 years
- 5-10 years

3. Do you apply the budgetary approach in your organization? (Tick where applicable)

- Yes
- No

4. If you chose No, give a reason for your answer

.....

5. Which role or position best describes your current role in the agricultural start-up? (Tick where applicable)

- Accountant
- Secretary
- Treasurer
- Manager
- Founder

6. What is the name and location of your start-up?

.....

Section 2:

Evaluating Current Budgeting Practices Objective 1 aims to critically evaluate the existing budgeting practices employed by agricultural start-ups in Uganda.

7. What types of budgeting practices or methods are currently employed by your agricultural start-up? (Tick where applicable)

- Incremental
- Zero based
- Mixed
- Do not know

8. In your opinion, what are the strengths and weaknesses of the budgeting practices currently used in your agricultural start-up?

.....

9. Would you say that budgeting improved your financial performance (Tick where applicable)

- True
- False

10. Give a reason for your answer

.....

.....

Section 3:

To analyze the specific financial challenges and dilemmas faced by agricultural start-ups in Uganda that can be mitigated through the effective implementation of budgeting practices, here are the top five questions to include in your questionnaire:

11. Have you faced difficulties in managing cash flow within your agricultural start-up? If so, please describe the nature of these challenges.

.....

.....

12. Do you struggle with cost control or cost management in your agricultural operations? If yes, can you provide examples of areas where you have encountered challenges?

.....

.....

13. Have you encountered situations where you had insufficient funds to meet essential operational needs or invest in growth opportunities? Please describe any specific instances where you believe proper budgeting would have helped?

.....

.....

14. In your opinion, how could the implementation of budgeting practices improve the financial stability and resilience of your agricultural start-up?

Section 4;

15. Identifying what Budgeting tools you use (Tick where applicable)

- Exel
- Google sheets
- Colour coded files
- Paper cash templates
- Other (Please specify)

16. What hindrances do you encounter while using this method?

.....

17. Of the above methods, which one would you prefer and why?

.....

END. Thank you.

Research timeline

PERIOD	ACTIVITY
June 1st-June	Start (Cover page, Acknowledgements and Introduction)

July 1st-July 30th	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Introduction, editing and referencing ● Literature review start <p>-Find relevant Articles</p> <p>-Edit</p> <p>-Referencing</p> <p>-Submit the Introduction and literature review drafts on Turnitin</p>
August 20th-September 30th	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Methodology (Introduction) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Find relevant articles -Prepare the Questionnaire -Identify the start-ups for participation -send Consent forms -Request consent from Interviewees -Schedule interview calls -Refine the methodology chapter -Reference <p>Submit the Methodology draft on Turnitin</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Checking and arranging the data collected <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Present the collected data -Start Data analysis
October 1st-October 25th	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Start Conclusions <p>Give recommendations</p> <p>State strength and limitations of the study</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Edit and the reference ● Submit the conclusions draft on turnitin.

October 25th-November 10th	-Attach Appendices -Final editing and refining
November 13th	Submit the first project Draft
November 14th	Submit the Final Project draft.

It emphasizes that these stakeholders contribute to and are affected by the success of the business, and their interests should be taken into account in decision-making processes